

Tabla. Cadena de búsqueda adaptada para cada base de datos.

No	Base de datos	Cadena de búsqueda adaptada	Fecha de búsqueda
1	Google Scholar	"Prompt engineering" AND "automatic code generation" AND "software development"	09/03/2026
2	IEEE	"Prompt engineering" in Anything AND "automatic code generation" in Anything AND "software development" in Anything	09/03/2026
3	Web of Science	((ALL=(Prompt engineering)) AND ALL=(automatic code generation)) AND ALL=(software development)	09/03/2026
4	Science Direct	"Prompt engineering" AND "automatic code generation" AND "software development"	09/03/2026
5	ACM Digital Library	[All: "prompt engineering"] AND [All: "automatic code generation"] AND [All: "software development"] AND [E-Publication Date: (01/01/2020 TO 09/03/2026)]	09/03/2026
6	Scopus	(TITLE-ABS-KEY ("Prompt engineering") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ("automatic code generation") AND TITLE-ABS-KEY ("software development")) AND PUBYEAR > 2019	09/03/2026
7	Springer	"Prompt engineering" AND "automatic code generation" AND "software development"	09/03/2026